

[Home](#) > [the Path](#) > [Shifu's Blog](#) >

The 11 Factors, 8 Awarenesses, and 3 Bodhi

posted Oct 20, 2010, 1:27 PM by S RC [updated Nov 1, 2010, 2:27 AM]

Once again, more information on how 11 and 8 keep showing up.

The information from this article comes from either the Lotus Sutra - if you want more direct reading - or from the study of martial arts and mysticism in general. I would say it is superfluous, but once again, those who know of these have an enormous advantage in knowing about them personally rather than living without the knowledge at all and bouncing around life like a buoy in a stormy sea.

The 11 Factors

Originally the Lotus Sutra and the sagely inheritors: T'ien Tai, Dengyo, and Nichiren Daishonin

called it the Ten Factors. We know from the Law of Relativity that this is because of the 10 humanly worlds are actually the first 10 vibratory realms of the Universe, the 11th being the Beyond or God or whatever you wish to call this singularity that contains and manifests all things.

It is through the 11 factors that it manifests all things, and science has forever been concerned with identifying these things, naming them, etc... but only in the Lotus Sutra and the commentaries of the above Buddhas do we see them listed skillfully and succinctly.

Here they are in verse form: Sho ho jisso, sho i shoho, nyo ze so, nyo ze sho, nyo ze tai, nyo ze riki, nyo ze sa, nyo ze in, nyo ze en, nyo ze ka, nyo ze ho, nyo ze honmak kuykyo to.

It means "this reality consists of:

1. Appearance
2. Nature
3. Entity
4. Power
5. Influence
6. Inherent Cause
7. Relation
8. Latent Effect
9. Manifest Effect
10. Consistency

11. From beginning to end

The last "Factor" has been split into its two yin-yang parts.

Science, as a rule is concerned with the study of the first four and, politics with the power and influence, religion with causes and effects, sociology and medicine with relation and latent effects, and physics with the sixth through tenth. But only sages seem to be concerned with all of them.

Lets look at each specifically.

Appearance is easy enough: it's what you see. But also it's what you can't see with your naked eye but only with your mind's eye, such as ideas, dreams, visions, imagination, and theories such as atomic, string, evolution, etc... which one cannot observe in real time but only with instrumentation and special methods. People often forget the things we've taken faith in and take for granted are really still just as fictional as magic or ghosts, because you do not perceive them directly but through your mental faculties which are as deluded as a drunk sailor mistaking a manatee for a mermaid.

Nature is the matter of those things which are found to act upon their own accord. It also manifests the 8 Laws. Entity is the divisible aspect of phenomena such as table, chair, tree, cat, person, whale, planet, etc...

Power is the factor that is the manifestation of Qi, energy, work, forces, fields, or anything that exerts influence.

Influence is based upon relation in that one cannot influence another without the other, so there is also the need for power and entity.

Inherent cause is both blatantly obvious causes such as crimes or activities, but also the causes made by thinking, imagining etc.. from Appearance. The nature factor is that which makes the 8 Laws move to manifest your mind into causes. Even without acting things go in a certain direction based upon the polarity of your mind towards unity or division: criminality vs completeness and wholesomeness.

Relation is that whereby the Law of Relativity perpetuates the relative causes to their relative effects, and is a central aspect to the Law of Karma or Cause and Effect.

Latent effect is what you cannot see, manifest effect is what you can. This is both temporal (now versus too long in the future to remember) and also the divine vs the humanly knowable, which is again the Law of Relativity in action.

Consistency is a reference to the connected nature. It is also a double or triple meaning for the 10th realm or the world of Buddhahood which enables an enlightened mind to perceive the interconnectedness of all things with the mind's eye which is now called the Buddha Eye.

The second part of that statement is "from beginning to end" and obviously is speaking of the 11th realm or the Beyond. The beginning to end shows the Law of Conservation's manifestation in containing all things and there being no end: no genesis nor Big Bang nor Armageddon, except for mankind as a species¹. The method by which the first ten factors are then manifest is through the Law of Evolution, the yang aspect of this pair, and it is only through these 4 Heavenly Laws above mentioned² that the 11 factors manifest It All.

The 8 Awarenesses

In my martial arts sessions I only generally speak on the lower six, which of course are most pertinent to people in a self-defense situation. But technically speaking there are 8 whole awarenesses that make up the one thing people call Awareness. There are plenty of sub-awarenesses just as there are sublaws and human laws. But here I will list them all, and the Law/trigram that they most relate to

1. Nature - Karma because this law is the king just as our natures and Mother Nature rule us
2. Environment - Evolution because our environment is constantly changing and adapting, so must we.
3. Situation - Relativity because the situation is relative to the POV of the person experiencing it and the objective witness
4. Reality - Conservation because this Law governs all containment of the 3 planes, 8 dharma, 11 factors, realms, aspects, and dimensions and the three ratios (golden, fibonacci, and 5/90/5 aka bell curve)
5. Choice of perception - Vibration because we set our own vibration by what we perceive
6. Karmic - Rotation - our vibration and choice of perception is what guides the rotation of the 11 aspects and 12 linked chain to weave our karmic tapestry.
7. Self - Polarity because this Law represents illumination of Fire and the act of attaining bodhi (situationally or further) through perception of the choice one makes and the directions it leads.
8. Dharmic (law) - Harmony because the awareness of the 8 laws themselves enables one to exist in harmony.

The reason that none of them directly match with themselves in because there is a need to relate all laws to each other through the 11 factors and 11 realms, thus enabling us to perceive the 8 awarenesses.

Being Aware is basically another term for anuttara-samyak-sambodhi.

The Three Bodhi

The first bodhi consists of eliminating ignorance and is called extinguishment. This means knowing in no particular order:

1. **Four Noble Truths**
2. **Noble Eightfold Path**
3. **12 Linked Chain of Karma**
4. 3 Planes [of heaven, man, and earth]
5. 3 bodhi [aka anuttara samyak sambodhi or nirvana, Nirvana, and Parinirvana]
6. **8 Laws**
7. 8 Awarenesses
8. **8 Meditation levels**
9. **11 Realms of vibration**
10. 11 Factors
11. **11 Aspects of Karma**

The second bodhi consists of eliminating the divisiveness of the first bodhi and is known as near perfect enlightenment. The requirement of Nirvana is to exist at the same vibration with own's

environment. This is of course impossible at all time perse, because of the Law of Relativity. BUT however since each world contains the other 10 worlds and 10 factors and 3 planes² then one can be empty or ordinary and also have bodhi accessible at any time via the 8 Awarenesses and the use of the Buddha Eye.

Thus the third bodhi is known as perfect enlightenment and is the act of Nirvana and Parinirvana (death in this state aka the Return). It is a matter of wisely applying bodhi, concealing it at times and revealing it other times, always expediently, and always with kindness, compassion and without aggression or retribution, which divide. This bodhi is a lifetime of practice. By not sitting in the seat unless one should, it opens the door for others to as well.

Upon death the right frame of mind is thought to carry over with one's soul (or souls) into the heavens and the next life (lives) and thus one perpetuates the precise ratio of the Tathagata Curve with one's own life and actions. After all 5% of the people are enlightened at any one time and carry 95% of the energy, whilst 90% of people in the Universe carry 4% and the last 5% only 1%.

This is because the fundamental nature of God is love and goodness, so only 5% of his body culls, the other 95% creates and evolves new things. But that is a discussion for another time.